

Localized Learning Activity Sheets and Learners' Competency in Sequence in Forming Rules, Expressions and Equations

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Abstract. This study examined the effectiveness of localized learning activity sheets in improving the competency of Grade 6 learners in sequence in forming rules, expressions, and equations at Castro Elementary School during School Year 2025-2026. The study aimed to address the learners' difficulties in mastering basic algebraic concepts by using contextualized and culturally relevant instructional materials connected to their daily experiences and environment. Using a quantitative quasi-experimental pretest and posttest design, the study involved twenty-eight learners identified as needing support in the least mastered competency. A validated teacher made test was used to gather data before and after the intervention, which were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that learners initially demonstrated low competency with 31.57 mean with most unable to reach mastery levels. After the implementation of the localized learning activity sheets, learners showed a modest improvement, reflected in an increase having a 38.36 mean score and a reduction in extremely low performance. Although most remained within the low and average levels, with a computed t-value of -4.10 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the improvement was statistically significant, indicating that the intervention had a positive effect on learners' understanding. The study concludes that localized learning activity sheets are effective in enhancing learners' competency, particularly in supporting both procedural and conceptual understanding. However, these materials alone are not sufficient to achieve higher mastery levels and should be supported with guided instruction and continuous practice. Overall, the use of contextualized materials provides a meaningful approach to developing algebraic thinking among learners.

Introduction

Mathematics enhances students' ability to think logically, solve math-related problems and analyze. The development of these abilities is becoming even more important due to the increasing complexity and technological nature of the world we live in today. Although the contributions of Mathematics are widely recognized, the outcomes of large-scale assessments continue to reveal serious gaps in student's level of Mathematical competence. Students often experience difficulty with handling tasks requiring a strong comprehension of material along with flexibility to manipulate procedures. In addition, PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment), TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study) and other studies indicate that students frequently encounter problems with higher order thinking skills such as identifying patterns, solving algebraic equations and demonstrating other types of advanced mathematical thinking (OECD, 2023a, 2023b, IEA, 2024). Similar issues were identified in the Philippines. A recent report from SEA-PLM revealed low levels of proficiency in Math among primary school aged students in tasks involving reasoning and abstraction (Department of Education et al., 2021).

A major factor contributing to student's inability to successfully apply learned knowledge is the disparity between their procedural knowledge and conceptual understanding. While some learners are able to complete processes or perform calculations accurately, they rarely demonstrate a full comprehension of the underlying concepts. This lack of connection

typically inhibits their ability to apply previously acquired knowledge in new and/or novel situations. Furthermore, students' ability to utilize what they have learned in meaningful ways is hindered by this same conceptual/procedural disconnect (Lenz et al., 2024). Algebraic thinking involves several skills such as establishing relationships within sequences, generalizing patterns and expressing those relationships in symbolic forms. Unfortunately, research shows that students often fail to recognize connections within sequences, establish rules based upon observed patterns and express these relationships in symbolic forms. All of these skills are necessary components for developing an effective algebraic thinker (Anaya et al., 2024; Jamil et al., 2025).

When instructional methods rely almost exclusively on abstract and decontextualized techniques, this issue becomes further exacerbated. In many classrooms, especially in rural communities or schools that have limited resources, most curriculum-based learning materials are standardized and separated from students' everyday life. As a result, students may view math as uninteresting or irrelevant, leading to disengagement with lessons and poor comprehension. At Castro Elementary School in Biruk, Dupax del Sur, Nueva Vizcaya, this challenge was illustrated by the fact that a review of mastery data showed that students performed poorly in competencies related to sequences, rules, expressions and equations. This illustrates the need for methodologies that will allow educators to teach math concepts in a manner that will be more meaningful and applicable to their students.

Contextualized learning is one methodology that has been gaining increased attention. Contextualized learning allows teachers to link mathematical concepts to students' environments, culture and everyday experiences. As a result, students are better able to relate math concepts to their own experiences, thus creating greater interest and a deeper understanding of the concepts being taught. Research indicates that contextualized teaching improves students' scores and creates more meaningful learning (Diago & Dillo, 2022; Ogates et al., 2023). The Department of Education in the Philippines has also placed great emphasis on utilizing localized learning materials that meet the needs of students and take into account their cultural backgrounds as stated in policies such as the Learning Continuity Plan and accompanying guidelines (Department of Education, 2020; Department of Education, 2016).

The idea of using Locally Developed Learning Activity Sheets (LLAS) as an example of this approach is due to its application of math-related activities that utilize culturally relevant examples from the daily life experience of learners. Teachers have the opportunity to create lesson plans that apply real-life connections to abstract ideas by utilizing the local theme, language, and content included in the development of LLAS. Additionally, there are numerous studies that support that if designed properly, LLAS will enhance students' abilities to learn complex subjects such as algebraic expressions and equations by providing them with a structured environment for learning and additional support throughout the process (Lacea & Buscano, 2023; Suguitan & Natividad, 2022).

Cognitive Learning Theory and Constructivist Theory provide a theoretical base for using LLAS. Cognitive Learning Theory emphasizes the active role that learners assume in processing and organization of new information. Constructivists emphasize that knowledge is constructed through meaningful learning experiences (Taber, 2024). Thus, when students engage with learning materials that represent their everyday experiences, they are more likely to create connections between new concepts and prior knowledge. This facilitates a deeper understanding of course material and increases retention over time. Moreover, this type of learning strategy is aligned with contemporary perspectives regarding best practices in mathematics education, emphasizing discovery learning, reasoning and conceptual learning over rote memorization.

Additionally, a focus on contextualized and inclusive learning practices serves to promote achievement of globally-defined educationally-relevant goals including SDG 4: Quality Education for All (UNESCO, n.d.). Enhancing elementary students' mathematical skill sets is a critical component toward achieving the long-term goal of SDG 4. Therefore, localized solutions such as LLAS provide an immediate and effective way to enhance both the quality and equity of education.

Although contextualized teaching has received considerable attention recently, very little research exists examining the effects of Localized Learning Activity Sheets on elementary learners' mathematical skills. More specifically, few studies exist examining the influence of these materials on students' capacity to generate rules, formulate expressions and equations. Given the significance of Grade 6 as a transitional period between basic arithmetic concepts and advanced algebraic thinking, this represents a critical gap.

Therefore, the purpose of this study was to examine the effectivity of Localized Learning Activity Sheets in enhancing Grade 6 learners' capabilities in sequences, rules, expressions and equations. Specifically, the study assessed learner's performance prior to use of LLAS and subsequent to use of LLAS with respect to learners' overall performance. Additionally, the study determined if there were statistically significant differences between the two points in terms of learners'

performance. Using an Input-Process-Output model, the study considered learners' entry-level skills in conjunction with localized learning materials as inputs; the pre-test/intervention/post-test sequence represented the input-process-output sequence; and improved learners' mathematical competence was identified as the desired output.

Due to the continuing challenges faced in mathematics education and the need for more responsive instructional methods than currently employed, this study provides timely insight into how localized materials can positively contribute to addressing these challenges. As a result of focusing on Grade 6 learners who possess foundational skills required for successful future academic endeavors, this study contributed to developing essential skills for future academic success.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' level of competency in sequence in forming rules, expression and equations before the use of LLAS?
2. What is the respondents' level of competency in sequence in forming rules, expression and equations after the utilization of LLAS?
3. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of competency in sequence in forming rules, expression and equations before and after the use of LLAS?

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the level of competency in sequence in forming rules, expression and equations before and after the use of LLAS.

Methodology

The study employed a quantitative, quasi-experimental research design to examine the effect of localized Learning Activity Sheets (LLAS) on the mathematics performance of Grade 6 learners, specifically in competencies related to sequences, rules, expressions, and equations. This design enabled the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data through pretest-posttest comparison, allowing the determination of significant differences in learners' performance before and after the intervention, as well as the exploration of relationships between scores using appropriate statistical techniques such as the paired-sample t-test and correlation analysis at a 0.05 level of significance. The research was conducted at Castro Elementary School in Biruk, Dupax del Sur, Nueva Vizcaya, a public institution under the Department of Education that serves a socioeconomically diverse population and is recognized for its active engagement in mathematics instruction and academic competitions. The school's availability of instructional resources, including multimedia tools and innovative teaching practices, along with a supportive and collaborative professional environment, made it a suitable site for implementing and evaluating the intervention.

The participants consisted of 28 Grade 6 learners (16 males and 12 females), selected through purposive sampling and total enumeration based on their need for improvement in the least mastered competency identified through prior assessments. Inclusion criteria required that learners had completed prerequisite mathematics modules, were actively participating in regular instruction, and demonstrated low mastery in the targeted competency. Data were collected using a 50-item teacher-made test aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) and supported by a Table of Specifications to ensure balanced coverage of six sub-competencies, namely identifying patterns, describing sequence rules, using tables or diagrams, writing expressions, formulating equations, and determining the *n*th term. The instrument underwent expert validation to ensure content accuracy, clarity, and alignment, and learner performance was interpreted using mastery level descriptors based on Department of Education standards.

Grade 6	Population	Sample	Percentage
Male	16	16	57%
Female	12	12	43%
Total	28	28	100%

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents

Data gathering followed a structured procedure beginning with securing administrative approval and informed consent from parents and participants, ensuring adherence to ethical standards. A validated pretest was administered to establish

baseline competency levels, followed by the implementation of the localized Learning Activity Sheets during regular mathematics instruction, where lessons were contextualized to learners' real-life experiences to enhance conceptual understanding. After the intervention period, a posttest using the same validated instrument was administered to measure learning gains. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, and mean, to describe learner performance, and inferential statistics, particularly the paired-sample t-test, to determine the significance of differences between pretest and posttest scores. Throughout the study, ethical considerations were strictly observed, including voluntary participation, confidentiality, anonymity through coded identifiers, secure data handling, and the right of participants to withdraw at any stage without penalty, ensuring the integrity and reliability of the research process.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1. Respondents' level of competency in sequence in forming rules, expression and equations before the use of LLAS

Competency Level	Frequency	Percentage
Mastered (96% - 100%)	0	0
Closely Approximating Mastery (86%-95%)	0	0
Moving Towards Mastery (66% - 85%)	0	0
Average (35% - 65 %)	9.00	32.14%
Low (15% - 34%)	19.00	67.86%
Very Low (5% - 14%)	0	0
Absolutely No Mastery (0 - 4%)	0	0
Mean		31.57%
Standard Deviation		10.96%
Qualitative Description		Low

Table 2: Summary of respondents' level of competency before the use of LLAS

The results of the study present a clear progression in the competency of Grade 6 learners in understanding sequences in forming rules, expressions, and equations before and after the utilization of localized Learning Activity Sheets (LLAS), as well as the statistical significance of the observed changes. Prior to the intervention, learners demonstrated generally low levels of competency, with 67.86% classified under the low category and 32.14% under the average level, and none reaching higher mastery levels. The computed mean score of 31.57% (SD = 10.96) confirms that the group, as a whole, had limited foundational understanding of pattern recognition and algebraic representation. This distribution suggests that learners struggled with transitioning from concrete arithmetic concepts to abstract algebraic thinking, a difficulty widely reported in mathematics education literature. The absence of learners in mastery levels indicates insufficient development of prerequisite cognitive skills such as generalization and symbolic reasoning, reinforcing the need for structured instructional support. From a theoretical standpoint, this condition reflects the principles of cognitive learning theory, where inadequate scaffolding and excessive cognitive load hinder learners' ability to process and internalize complex concepts. The findings also align with broader educational reports indicating persistent gaps in foundational numeracy and reasoning skills among learners, particularly in contexts where instruction remains abstract and decontextualized.

Problem 2. Respondents' level of competency in sequence in forming rules, expression and equations after the use of LLAS

Reading Level	Frequency	Percentage
Mastered (96% - 100%)	0	0
Closely Approximating Mastery (86%-95%)	0	0
Moving Towards Mastery (66% - 85%)	2	7.14
Average (35% - 65 %)	13	46.43
Low (15% - 34%)	13	46.43
Very Low (5% - 14%)	0	0
Absolutely No Mastery (0 - 4%)	0	0
Mean		38.36
Standard Deviation		14.27
Qualitative Description		Average

Table 3: Summary of respondents' level of competency after the use of LLAS

Following the implementation of the localized Learning Activity Sheets, learners' performance showed a modest but meaningful improvement. The posttest results revealed a redistribution of learners across competency levels, with 46.43% classified as average, 46.43% remaining at the low level, and 7.14% reaching the moving towards mastery category. The mean score increased to 38.36 (SD = 14.27), indicating a shift from low to average competency. Notably, no learners were categorized under very low or absolutely no mastery, suggesting that the intervention was effective in preventing extremely low performance levels. However, the concentration of learners within the lower categories and the absence of high mastery levels indicates that while progress occurred, it was not sufficient to achieve advanced understanding for most learners. The increased standard deviation further suggests variability in learning gains, implying that the effectiveness of the intervention differed across individuals. These results highlight that while the contextualized and structured design of LLAS supported engagement and initial comprehension, some learners required additional scaffolding, guided practice, and reinforcement to fully grasp higher-order concepts such as algebraic generalization. This pattern is consistent with cognitive learning principles, which emphasize gradual knowledge construction and the importance of aligning instructional complexity with learners' readiness levels. The findings also reflect existing evidence that contextualized instructional materials can improve engagement and understanding but must be complemented by sustained instructional support to achieve mastery.

Problem 3: Summary of t-test computation on the difference in the respondents' level of competency in sequence in forming rules, expression and equations before and after the use of localized Learning Activity Sheets

Test	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean Diff	Computed t-value	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Pretest	31.57	10.96	-6.78	-4.10	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis	Significant

Table 4: Summary on the difference in respondents' level of competency before and after the use of LLAS

To determine whether the observed improvement was statistically significant, a paired-sample t-test was conducted comparing pretest and posttest scores. The results showed a mean increase of 6.78 points, from 31.57 to 38.36, with a computed t-value of -4.10 and a p-value of less than 0.001. Since the p-value is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a statistically significant difference between learners' performance before and after the intervention. This finding provides strong empirical evidence that the use of localized Learning Activity Sheets had a positive effect on learners' competency. The improvement suggests that the intervention successfully facilitated learning by making abstract mathematical concepts more accessible through contextualization and structured tasks. By connecting mathematical ideas to learners' real-life experiences, the LLAS likely enhanced engagement and supported meaningful learning, consistent with constructivist and cognitive learning perspectives.

Moreover, the significant improvement aligns with previous studies demonstrating that contextualized and activity-based instructional materials enhance mathematical understanding and problem-solving skills. The structured nature of LLAS allowed learners to gradually build their understanding, moving from pattern recognition to rule formulation and symbolic representation. However, the variability in posttest scores indicates that learning gains were not uniform, suggesting the need for differentiated instruction and additional reinforcement for learners who continue to struggle. This also underscores the importance of combining well-designed instructional materials with effective teaching strategies, including guided instruction, feedback mechanisms, and opportunities for practice.

Overall, the findings confirm that localized Learning Activity Sheets are an effective instructional intervention for improving learners' competency in sequences and algebraic thinking. While the improvement was statistically significant, the relatively modest increase in mean scores and the continued concentration of learners in lower competency levels indicate that further refinement of the intervention is necessary. Enhancing scaffolding, incorporating more interactive and higher-order tasks, and providing sustained instructional support may lead to greater and more consistent learning gains. These results contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting contextualized and learner-centered approaches in mathematics education, particularly in addressing foundational gaps in algebraic reasoning.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were derived:

1. The learners lack the necessary foundational skills in pattern recognition and algebraic representation before the intervention. Therefore, there is a need for structured, contextualized, and learner centered materials to improve competency in forming mathematical rules, expressions, and equations.

2. The utilization of LLAS contributed to a slight improvement in learners' competency in forming rules, expressions, and equations from sequences, but was not sufficient to achieve higher levels of mastery. Most learners still struggled with deeper conceptual understanding, particularly in transitioning from pattern recognition to abstract mathematical representation.
3. LLAS significantly improve learners' competency in sequence in forming mathematical rules, expressions, and equations. The intervention not only supported procedural learning but also strengthened conceptual understanding through structured and contextualized tasks.

Recommendations

1. Teachers are encouraged to integrate LLAS to provide clearer guidance and connect mathematical concepts to learners' real-life experiences.
2. Teachers may supplement LLAS with guided instruction, differentiated activities, and continuous feedback to better support learners with varying abilities.
3. Teachers are encouraged to integrate LLAS into their instruction to make mathematical concepts more relatable and easier to understand, while also providing additional support to learners who may need reinforcement.
4. School administrators may actively support the development and implementation of resources that incorporate scaffolding and differentiated learning, ensuring that lessons can address the varied abilities and needs of learners.
5. Future researchers may look more closely at the long-term impact of localized learning materials, such as LLAS, on students' mathematical competence, particularly in algebra.
6. Future studies could explore how LLAS can be combined with other teaching strategies to identify approaches that more effectively enhance learners' skills.
7. Incorporating features into the LLAS that promote parental involvement such as guided prompts, home-based tasks, and simple monitoring checklists, can help reinforce learners' understanding beyond the classroom.
8. Future research could focus on specific sub-competencies within the topic to pinpoint learners' areas of greatest difficulty, offering a clearer basis for targeted remediation and instructional improvement.
9. The LLAS can be further improved by refining its content, structure, and activities to enhance clarity, increase engagement, and better align with learners' needs and the intended competencies.
10. The LLAS may be subjected to a quality assurance review by the Department of Education to ensure alignment with curriculum standards and to support possible adoption and wider use across the division.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.